

SDE / TRE Definition Working Group

Initial Community Survey results

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1 Overview

The SDE / TRE Definitions Working group is focused on clarifying the terms used WITHIN the UK TRE community especially when different parts are performed by different organisations. SDEs and TREs are different, but views on how and the extent to which they differ are varied.

This Working Group came from discussion proposals made during the SATRE project in 2023 and the UK TRE conference in Swansea ¹. A series of open online discussion groups were held in early Jan 2024 and from two such events, focused on SDE / TRE Definitions it became clear that there was a lot of agreement that there were key differences in SDE and TREs but that this separation was to help INTERNAL Community discussions and not to confuse the public ². One of the initial proposals was to gauge the level of agreement within the UK TRE community for definitions of terms in this area.

A survey ³ was produced to start assessing the level of agreement to a starter set of definitions and the results indicate a solid base to develop from. The survey questions, for each of the three core components that were scored by respondents, are shown in Annex A: and the result summary shared here in section 2 *Analysis Results*: (from the 16 initial respondents).

As a result of the first analysis a second survey was created that refined the questions and positioned the respondents with the main conclusions of the first survey; introducing the Data and Research Zones as a formal terminology component. This survey garnered an additional 3 responses (more from operational respondents) whose summary was as equally, positive to the model, albeit there is still a variety of views on specifics, and more work is needed for complete alignment.

2 Analysis Results:

2.1 Method:

The quantitative results from the survey are held in the sheet “Data” within the excel results file. This data was pivoted into the other sheets and configured to show the individual questions relating to each of the three core components asked about in the survey:

1. Secure Data Environment (SDE)
2. Trusted Research Environment Platform (TREP)
3. Project Trusted Research Environment (PTRE)

¹ at Event Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/8376131> and specific talk by Pete Barnsley https://zenodo.org/records/8376131/files/Pete%20Barnsley%20Crick_TRE_Swansea_LightningTalk_04_09_2023.pptx?download=1

²

https://github.com/FrancisCrickInstitute/UK_TRE/tree/main/SDE%20TRE%20Definitions%20Working%20Group

³ <https://forms.office.com/e/sCTnuJZgbP> and follow up <https://forms.office.com/e/VaB9202cpB>

For each the pivot was set up to offer the level of agreement / disagreement for the questions as well as the Overall agreement / disagreement. And an additional sheet was prepared configured with the Overall agree/disagree scale for the three core components in the survey (SDE, TREP, PTRE).

The second stage of analysis was to colour label each of the combinations of agree / disagree based on some base rules.

Five colours were chosen where an agree / disagree equates to 1 point and a strongly agree/disagree counts for 2 points.

- Dark Green: all are 'agree' – either strongly agree or agree
- Light Green: More 'agree' than 'disagree'.
- Yellow: Same level of 'agree' and 'disagree'
- Orange: More 'disagree' than 'agree'
- Red: all are 'disagree'

The final step was to aggregate categories into 'Generally agree', 'Middle Road' and 'Disagree'

Because the respondents had added lots of rich information explaining their scoring, qualitative analysis was also possible. This is provided in the sheet "Pivot tool Comments" and is set up to show the text relating to the question

"Please help us.

What points do you want to raise about your disagreement (or agreement) with the XXX definition"

for all the three core components in the survey (SDE, TREP, PTRE). The three questions are sorted using the "Organisation name"

No formal analysis of this quantitative data is presented here, except to bring out the following general findings:

- Many comments flag that it is the labels (SDE, TRE) that are a sticking point not the descriptive statements for each.
- The results suggest a polarised viewpoint on the scope and definitions – either like it or not at all.

2.2 Quantitative results:

The following chart and table summarise the different aggregated summaries for the three core components in the survey (SDE, TREP, PTRE along with the overall summary of the three.

Core component in survey	Analysed aggregate score (sample N=16)		
	Generally Agree	Middle Road	Disagree
Secure Data Environment (SDE)	75%	6%	19%
Trusted Research Environment Platform (TREP)	75%	13%	13%
Project Trusted Research Environment (PTRE)	69%	25%	25%
All Overall rating for three core components	50%	13%	38%

Figure 1: Analysis results from initial community survey on definitions of SDE/TREP and PTRE

For all three core components the agreement was ~70% +/- 5% and the disagreement was ~20% +/- 10%. This suggests a good buy-in to the proposed definitions, which is reinforced by the 50% general agreement overall across all three definitions.

Combined with the qualitative conclusions from looking at the comments, this suggests that the community has general agreement separating these core components out.

2.3 Conclusions:

The significant macro conclusion is the degree of agreement in respondents to the proposed separation and definitions.

Three next steps are proposed:

- 1) Based on feedback from the community a refinement to the labels being used is suggested. The new labels are proposed to be 'Data Zone' and 'Research Zone' – proposed by one of the survey responders.
- 2) What is also suggested by the respondents is to refinement of the definitions and terms as a number of constructive suggestions were made that did not conflict with the definition structure.
 - a. An additional related step is to do more analysis of the responses to identify the major points of disagreement, and liaise with responders (if they said they would be happy for follow-on discussion) to understand more.
- 3) A resubmission of this survey to the community is also suggested as a next step.

Following returns from an initial community survey, this document will use the term '**Data Zone**' when referring to a secure data environment⁴, and the term '**Research Zone**' when

⁴ Previously referred to as the Secure Data Environment (SDE) in the survey
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referring to the area where research analysis is done in a trusted research environment⁵. See Figure 2

Figure 2: Illustrative diagram to help with the context of the 'Data Zone' and the 'Research Zone' for Working Grp

3 How and Why the Data Zone and Research Zone are different:

Based on the survey input questions the characteristics of the different zones and **the three key elements** are:

Data Zone:

1) The secure data environment / data library

1. Curation of data from respected operational sources – such as a health care setting
2. Creation of groups of data items and fields, specific to an approved project's purpose. Making safe data.
3. Sharing this set of defined fields to the project (through an information governance process).
4. The Data zone is a master repository of data and so focuses on STORAGE with compute used for ETL/ELT⁶ data processing activities
5. The Data zone operator may also act as data controllers implementing Information Governance processes.

Research Zone:

There are **two elements** to the research Zone, organisations that operate platform settings to support a trusted research environment for a project, and then the specific project TRES that are bespoke to the actual project and the participants of that project

2) The trusted research platform:

6. Sets up and manages the safe setting facilities for each and every safe project that is accredited to be operating on the platform.

⁵ Previously referred to as the Trusted Research Environment Platform (TREP) and Project Trusted Research Environment (PTRE) combined.

⁶ **ELT** = Extraction Load Transform, **ETL** = Extract Transform Load.

7. Sets up specific, tailored, user roles and grants these roles to approved people in RPOs that are allowed access to project TREs on the platform: safe RPOs and safe people.
8. Provides computing processing and storage for the data, and allows access to the specific datasets granted to the specific projects.
9. Offers billing and accounting for the use of the compute processing
10. Provides audit and compliance reporting for all projects that are running on this platform.

3) The Project trusted research environment:

11. Offers a specific closed and controlled space for the researchers to access the controlled data
12. Offers space for each project partner to securely host data they own and share it to the project researchers.
13. Ensuring safe outputs through suitable practices and controls, which the project manages.

Why different:

Some of the functional drivers (also see Figure 3) that prompt this separation of concerns between these three key elements are:

- **Federation:** Research projects now invariably need access to multiple different datasets from different places. The research questions are becoming broader and needing a wider variety of data types to be answered. A federation of providers is needed rather than only supporting the model of single provider solutions.
- **Engineering Skill sets:** The data engineering skills within a Data Zone player are very different from that within a Research Zone player. The data zone engineering focusses on industrial scale robust documented pipelines coding. The Research Zone is more experimental in nature, with the focus of the code pipelines being the development of data tools (machine learning) and testing hypotheses.
- **Governance:** The Data Zone player has a big focus on Information Governance. They are focused on securing access to specific selected datasets for each project, and the application of controller rules and restrictions, and managing the data sharing pipeline agreements that facilitate those sets. The Research Zone is focused on ensuring output controls and safe researcher behaviour is operating.
- **Computing and planning drivers and change timescales:** The Data Zone players are focused on storage costs and technology changes for this task which vary more slowly than compute. Their planning is driven by the growth in data volumes and what drives this row volume. The Research Zone player is focused on the faster computing needs which change more quickly and is driven by the mix of analytics demand from the portfolio of research projects being supported (on the platform for the project). And they are needing to support the software solutions (licenses) needed for the analysis.
- **Isolation of research projects** from each other for risk management and legal requirements.

- The costs are driven by relatively simple driver parameters.

Cost type	Unit	Timescales for change	Scaling Drivers and parameters	Illustrative / Indicative	
				Data Zone	Research Zone
Salary	Hours	Long: years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow varying: No and skill of people * inflation * cost of skills 	50%	50%
Storage	Tera Byte	Long: every ~10 year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow varying: New data rows / day (equates to no of citizens / objects * rate of illness / activity) 	80%	20%
Compute	Giga-FLOPS	Short: 2-3yr full refresh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast varying: No of research projects * Amount of data * Complexity of Question * Transfer data costs + <i>Researcher Costs:</i> Time spent on research progress / Total time spent. 	20%	80%
Licences	Seat / usage	Short-Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast varying: new releases, upgrades but Slow varying: Usage pattern due to learning curve and experience / confidence in certain tooling No of researchers 	10%	90%

Figure 3: The cost drivers and their differences across the Data and Research Zones: Colours designate: **black** – people; **red** – memory storage; and **blue** – processing related.

Definitions of the three elements:

The definitions of these Zones and the objects within them are summarised in Figure 4. Instead of using a set of text glossary labels, an ontological type structure is used to separate connections. Three coloured areas show the delineation and pairing of the three key component elements. This type of diagram is read by using the box objects as nouns and the lines to connect the nouns using the words nearest each box as the 'verb' or action.

Figure 4: Ontology definitions of the three components within the Data and Research Zones

So, for example:

Data Zone – SDE / Data Library

A **data object** belongs to a **collection** (that holds one or more data objects) which is controlled by an **Owning / Controlling organisation**. These data objects have **data field items** that can become a **shared data field item** when made available (to a project) as part of an **approved share to a project** approved by the Owning / Controlling organisation. The data object is housed in a **Data Library** that is accessed through a **Data Zone hosting platform** run by a **Data Zone Player** that controls its operation.

Research Zone – TRE Platform

A **TRE Platform player** is the controller of the operations of a **Research Zone trusted research environment platform** (TREP) which enables using IG workflows to create an **Approval** within it that triggers the creation of a **Research Project** (and all its facilities). The platform has defined **roles** within it. And the platform creates common **audit and log events** and **bill events**. These underpin **Audit & compliance reports** that are built from the events and **Invoices** that are made up of the bill events. Not shown but implicit is that the reports are made available to the project, and the invoices sent to the project **responsible organisation**.

Research Zone – Project TRE

A **Research Project** is created within the context of an **approval** which creates one and only one. **Researchers** are part of this project and adhere to the policy of a **Project Partner Organisation** that employs them. The research project is the responsibility of a **Responsible Organisation** which controls activity within the research project. As the researchers progress audit & log events and bill events become associated with the project, which are seen through the reports and invoices. The research project houses the **computing facilities** accessible only by the research project (and the associated researchers) to hold **new research data objects** which may have **shared data field items** tied to them as part of an **approved “share” to the project**. These **new research data objects** also have **new research data field items** that are also tied to them and which are owned by the research project that created them.

Differences to existing “TREs”

The present model may look very similar if not identical to this, but hopefully it is clear why it is not. Presently TRE operations are isolated and specific to the data Collections hosted in that facility. Projects are split, having a presence in each TRE / SDE that it requires data from, to accommodate this present operating model. An illustration of the present model is shown in Figure 5. Compare this to the model shown in Figure 2: the existing “TREs” have *“the project coming to the data”*, whereas this model has *“the data coming to the project”*. Both with the same security and control by owners.

Figure 5: Illustrative model of present TRE researcher experience

4 Conclusions:

There are important drivers that mean the UK TRE community need to architect and specific “TREs” in a more detailed way, separating out the three key elements

- The Data Zone (Secure data environment / data library)
- The Research Zone Trusted Research Environment Platform
- The Research Zone Project trusted research environment

These three will probably be operated by different players across the UK federation (extending also into the EU and world) that will come.

Information governance flows need to understand these elements separately and this should be helped by the ontological flows described in Figure 4. IG community interest groups are asked to establish how IG orchestration and workflow can cross over these boundaries and recognise their separation.

The SATRE work should also embed this set of distinctions within its framework. Adopting this will enable the critical move to federation. The SATRE related project work is asked to establish how the specification will recognise these separations within its federation model work, and accommodate players offering one or more of these positions to the federation for assessment.

The glossary work should adopt and adapt terms used here – adopt specifically the Data Zone and Research Zone three definitions on pages 7/8, and (by adaption as needed) ensure the clarity brought by the three elements and the set of ontological terms (see Figure 4) is maximised.

More work is expected and this set of definitions and separations will be refined over time as these works progress and complete.

Annex A: Questions scored by respondents for the three core components

The original survey was presented like this <https://forms.office.com/e/sCTnuJZgbP>. And based on the suggested nomenclature change to data Zone and Research Zone an amended survey was shared: <https://forms.office.com/e/VaB9202cpB>

Secure Data Environment (SDE):

Please say how much you agree with the following statements defining a Secure Data Environment (SDE)

SDE above definition OVERALL
SDE Curated data from respected sources
SDE A master repository of datasets
SDE provides Info Governance to manage access from TRE Platforms
SDE Creates dataset views for use by projects
SDE Often may hold a Data Controller role

Trusted Research Environment Platform (TREP)

Please say how much you agree with the following statements defining a Trusted Research Environment Platform (TREP)

TRE Platform above definition OVERALL
TREP Provides Safe settings for projects - setup / manage project TREs
TREP RPO accredited for their projects - safe projects and safe people
TREP Users with specified allowed roles
TREP Provides compute and storage for project data
TREP Billing and accounting support for projects
TREP Audit and Compliance reporting for projects

Project Trusted Research Environment (PTRE)

Please say how much you agree with the following statements defining a Project Trusted Research Environment (PTRE)

Project TRE above definition OVERALL
PTRE The TRE is specific to the project - having a collaboration space
PTRE Each project partner has a space connected to the collaboration
PTRE The project and project TRE has accountability for safe outputs